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RESEARCH ARTICLE

PWMF-ResMiniNet: A Novel Lightweight Deep Learning and Fusion Framework Combining Precision-Weighted Integration of Multiple CNNs for Wearable Sensor-Based Human Activity Recognition

MOHAMMAD SAKKA¹, OSAMA ORABI¹, YAZAN ALNAKRI¹,
AND MOHAMMAD REZA BAHRAMI^{1,2,3}

¹Cyber-Physical Laboratory, Innopolis University, 420500 Innopolis, Russia

²School of Engineering, Samarkand International University of Technology, Samarkand 140104, Uzbekistan

³Research Center of the Artificial Intelligence Institute, Innopolis University, 420500 Innopolis, Russia

Corresponding author: Mohammad Sakka (m.sakka@innopolis.university)

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ABSTRACT Human Activity Recognition (HAR) plays a vital role in healthcare, smart home, and security applications. Recent advances in sensor technology and machine learning have substantially enhanced HAR capabilities, particularly for continuous monitoring of elderly individuals. Time-series imaging and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been effectively applied to this task. In this study, we adapt these techniques to the underexplored and challenging GOTOV dataset and further develop a novel framework, **PWMF-ResMiniNet**, a lightweight yet highly accurate solution for HAR optimized for resource-constrained edge computing environments. The framework introduces two key innovations. First, the *Precision-Weighted Model Fusion* (PWMF) algorithm performs decision-level fusion of multiple sensor-specific CNNs by assigning adaptive per-class weights based on each model's validation precision, achieving state-of-the-art accuracy with zero additional computational cost while remaining interpretable and theoretically sound. Second, the *ResMiniNet* CNN architecture, inspired by the ResNet model, reduces trainable parameters by approximately 75% while maintaining competitive accuracy. Combined with Gramian angular field imaging, PWMF-ResMiniNet achieves over 90% F1-score on the GOTOV dataset—the highest reported accuracy on this dataset to date—and demonstrates consistent superiority over state-of-the-art methods such as HARDenseCNN and HART on the PAMAP2 and WISDM 2019 datasets. Moreover, the study discusses the limitations of the proposed framework and current HAR approaches, identifies open research challenges, and highlights promising directions for future investigation.

INDEX TERMS Human activity recognition (HAR), wearable sensors; multimodal sensor fusion, time-series imaging, Gramian angular field (GAF), convolutional neural networks (CNN), lightweight deep learning, precision-weighted model fusion (PWMF), edge computing, healthcare, AI assistive technology, GOTOV, PAMAP2, WISDM 2019.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Human activity recognition (HAR) plays a pivotal role in applications such as healthcare, surveillance, and sports

analytics [1], [2], [3]. The effectiveness of these applications depends heavily on the accuracy and robustness of HAR systems [4]. Researchers have explored various approaches, including wearable sensor data analysis [5], vision-based techniques [6], environmental sensors [7], smartphone-based systems [8], RF-based methods [9], IoT-based frameworks [10], and physiological monitoring [11]. To overcome the limitations of individual sensors, hybrid approaches that combine multiple modalities have also been investigated [12]. Among these, wearable sensors are particularly advantageous due to their ability to monitor body movements in real-time, provide localized measurements, and offer high accuracy. Their portability, cost-effectiveness, and scalability contribute to their widespread adoption [13].

Despite these advantages, achieving high-accuracy HAR with wearable sensors remains a challenge [4]. Traditional machine learning methods often depend on handcrafted features and manual preprocessing, which are time-consuming and may not generalize well [14]. In contrast, deep learning techniques, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), automatically extract discriminative features from raw data, reducing the reliance on domain-specific engineering [15]. One-dimensional CNNs (1D CNNs) are commonly used for temporal feature extraction from single-channel time series, but they struggle to capture complex spatio-temporal dependencies [16]. Two-dimensional CNNs (2D CNNs) address this limitation by modeling spatial and temporal relationships in transformed time series data [17]. Converting time series into two-dimensional images using techniques such as Gramian Angular Fields (GAF) enables the application of powerful image-based CNN architectures, improving the robustness and accuracy of HAR systems [18].

Since activity-specific movements are often localized, sensor placement greatly affects recognition performance. Utilizing multiple sensors placed at different body locations enables sensor-level fusion, allowing the system to leverage complementary information and enhance overall classification accuracy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents a comprehensive review of the relevant literature that underpins the current research. Key themes include the transformation of time series data into image-based representations, the application of deep learning techniques to such representations, and subsequent advancements in classification and recognition tasks. The discussion begins with an overview of methods for converting time series into image formats, enabling the use of convolutional architectures originally developed for computer vision.

A. TIME SERIES IMAGING

Time series data can be effectively transformed into two-dimensional representations to capture both temporal and frequency-domain features [19]. This transformation facilitates the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs),

FIGURE 1. Spectrogram imaging example.

FIGURE 2. Recurrence plot imaging example.

which have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in visual recognition tasks [19].

One widely adopted method is the spectrogram, introduced by Gabor [20]. This technique applies the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) to extract time-localized frequency spectra, which are then arranged into a 2D matrix—where the horizontal axis represents time and the vertical axis denotes frequency. This representation captures the signal's evolving spectral content (see Fig. 1).

Another technique is the recurrence plot, proposed by Eckmann et al. [21], which visualizes the recurrence of states in a dynamical system. For each time window, a recurrence event is identified if the distance between data points at different time steps falls below a predefined threshold. This results in a 2D binary matrix depicting recurrence patterns (see Fig. 2).

Wang and Oates [22] introduced the Gramian Angular Field (GAF), which maps time series data into polar coordinates—encoding each point as an angle and a radius. The angle represents the normalized time series value, while the radius denotes its timestamp. The resulting Gramian matrix captures angular relationships between all time point pairs, using either the cosine of angle summations (GASF) or the sine of angle differences (GADF).

In the same year, Wang and Oates [19] also proposed the Markov Transition Field (MTF), a technique that discretizes the time series into quantile bins and models the transition probabilities between these bins. These probabilities are encoded into a 2D matrix, where the pixel intensities reflect the likelihood of state transitions (see Fig. 3).

Through these imaging techniques, time series data can be reformulated as image inputs. This enables the use of

FIGURE 3. MTF imaging example.

well-established image-based deep learning methods for classification, anomaly detection, and pattern recognition tasks in domains such as human activity recognition.

B. CNN MODELS

While deep neural networks have shown exceptional performance across various domains, their conventional forms are not inherently optimized for spatial data such as images [23]. Traditional image feature extraction methods often rely on convolving images with handcrafted kernels designed to emphasize particular spatial patterns [24]. Notable examples include edge detectors such as the Sobel operator [25] and the Prewitt operator [26], which highlight intensity gradients. Gabor filters, originally proposed by Gabor [20], detect specific frequency and orientation content within localized regions of an image, making them suitable for texture analysis. Similarly, Local Binary Patterns (LBP), introduced by Ojala et al. [27], encode local texture by thresholding neighboring pixel intensities. Additional techniques like Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) [28] and Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) [29] extract keypoints and gradient-based features to represent object shape and orientation. These manually designed feature extraction algorithms have been widely used in classical computer vision pipelines.

However, selecting the optimal feature descriptor for a given task remains a non-trivial and often heuristic-driven process [30]. To overcome this limitation, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), first introduced by LeCun et al. [31], were developed to automatically learn hierarchical feature representations from raw image inputs. Unlike fixed kernels, CNNs employ learnable filters optimized during training to capture task-relevant features. This makes CNNs highly adaptable to diverse computer vision problems [15].

1) TIME SERIES IMAGING AND CNNs IN HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION (HAR)

In the context of Human Activity Recognition (HAR), time series imaging techniques allow sensor data from wearable devices to be converted into two-dimensional representations, facilitating the use of CNNs for feature extraction and classification. For example, Qin et al. [18] employed Gramian Angular Fields (GAF) [22] to transform multivariate sensor data into structured images. These image-based

representations were then processed using CNNs, enabling the automatic extraction of discriminative features and achieving high accuracy in HAR tasks.

A more comprehensive approach was proposed by Abdel-Basset et al. [32], who explored multiple time series imaging techniques for HAR. Their methodology included Recurrence Plots (RP) [21], which visualize repeated state patterns in a reconstructed phase space, and Markov Transition Fields (MTF) [19], which encode temporal dynamics as transition probability matrices. They also utilized Gramian Angular Fields (GAF) [22] and further investigated a fusion strategy that combines all three imaging modalities. The resulting images were analyzed using deep CNN architectures, demonstrating the effectiveness of multi-representation approaches in enhancing activity recognition performance.

C. FUSION

Machine learning models exhibit diverse strengths and limitations, and combining them through model fusion can enhance predictive performance by leveraging their complementary capabilities. Models may vary in architecture, training algorithms, input features, or data modalities. Fusing such heterogeneous models can result in more robust and generalized systems [33].

1) HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE ON MODEL FUSION

The concept of model fusion has undergone substantial evolution. In 1996, Breiman introduced Bootstrap Aggregating (Bagging), an ensemble meta-algorithm designed to improve classification and regression stability by reducing variance and overfitting [34]. This was later extended to the Random Forest algorithm in 2001, where multiple decision trees are trained independently and combined using majority voting [35]. Dietterich [36] also demonstrated the consistent performance advantages of ensemble models over single classifiers.

In the context of multimedia analysis, Atrey et al. [37] classified multimodal fusion techniques into three broad categories: feature-level, decision-level, and hybrid fusion. More recently, Boulahia et al. [38] proposed enhancements to early fusion techniques for multimodal action recognition. Their work introduced an intermediate fusion strategy and applied neural-based learning mechanisms for late fusion to address inherent limitations of traditional methods.

2) LEVELS OF FUSION

Bayouh et al. [39] further refined fusion methodologies by categorizing them into three levels:

- **Early Fusion (Feature-Level Fusion):** Merges multiple data types into a single input before training, typically via concatenation or averaging.
- **Late Fusion (Decision-Level Fusion):** Combines outputs from independently trained models using methods like voting, weighted averaging, or stacking for the final decision.

- **Hybrid Fusion:** Merges features at the input level and combines model outputs at the decision stage.

3) FUSION TECHNIQUES FOR HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION (HAR)

Fusion techniques have proven especially effective in Human Activity Recognition (HAR). For instance, Qin et al. [18] proposed a fusion-based HAR framework using data from a single wearable sensor. The sensor captured two complementary modalities: linear acceleration and angular velocity, which were independently transformed into image representations.

These modality-specific images were processed using a ResNet34-inspired CNN architecture [40]. The fusion was implemented via an additional layer inserted after the third convolutional block. Initially, each CNN stream was trained separately to capture modality-specific features. Subsequently, the fusion layer was trained to integrate these features, enabling the model to exploit cross-modal relationships. This two-stage training significantly improved activity classification performance.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the methodology and the principal theoretical foundations underlying the proposed approach.

A. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The overall framework of the proposed human activity recognition (HAR) system is depicted in Fig. 4. Tri-axial accelerometers were deployed at three distinct anatomical locations: the chest, wrist, and ankle. Each sensor captures continuous acceleration data along three orthogonal axes, forming independent time series. These time series are segmented using fixed-size sliding windows and subsequently transformed into two-dimensional images via the Gramian Angular Field (GAF) technique.

Independent convolutional neural network (CNN) models are trained for each sensor modality to classify the associated physical activity. Finally, the outputs of the three CNNs are integrated using a fusion strategy to produce the final activity classification.

B. DATASET DESCRIPTION

1) GOTOV DATASET

The GOTOV dataset was introduced by Paraschiakos et al. [41] as part of the “Growing Old TOgether Validation” (GOTOV) study, aimed at constructing a labeled human activity dataset specifically tailored for older adults. It contains data from 35 participants (14 female, 21 male), each performing 16 common daily activities while wearing four devices placed at six distinct body locations. Sensor placements are illustrated in Fig. 5. More comprehensive details can be found in the original publication [41].

The dataset is publicly available and provides tri-axial accelerometer data collected from three primary body

FIGURE 4. Overall framework of the proposed human activity recognition system.

FIGURE 5. Sensor placements in the GOTOV study, adapted from [41].

locations—ankle, chest, and wrist—across 16 annotated activity classes. Its diversity in activity types and sensor placements makes it a valuable benchmark for evaluating multi-sensor fusion and body-location-specific modeling strategies in human activity recognition (HAR).

Despite its comprehensive nature, the GOTOV dataset has received limited attention compared to more widely adopted datasets such as UCI HAR [42], PAMAP2 [43], and WISDM [44]. Most studies using GOTOV focus on classical machine learning approaches with handcrafted

features. For example, Paraschiakos et al. [41] applied decision tree classifiers after grouping similar activities to reduce the number of classes. While this approach improved performance, it required simplifying the classification task, thereby limiting generalizability to the original 16-class problem.

Okai et al. [45] employed deep recurrent neural networks—specifically GRUs and LSTMs—and achieved promising results. However, these models required the full dataset and were computationally intensive. Recurrent architectures, in general, are known for their high computational demands [46, p. 57967] and lower interpretability [47, p. 15457]. Moreover, the fusion strategy adopted in these studies relied solely on early fusion, using simple concatenation of feature vectors—a method that may not effectively capture inter-modal relationships. The best F-score reported in such approaches was approximately 84.5%, which may be insufficient for real-world HAR applications that demand high accuracy and efficiency.

2) RESEARCH GAP

Although Human Activity Recognition (HAR) has been extensively studied, the GOTOV dataset—featuring multi-sensor data from multiple body locations—remains underutilized in the literature. Many existing studies either simplify the task or struggle with inherent challenges such as the high number of activity classes (16), class imbalance, and subtle inter-class similarities in movement patterns. Furthermore, there is a lack of lightweight, interpretable models capable of delivering high classification accuracy without relying on complex architectures or extensive data preprocessing. These limitations highlight the need for an efficient and robust approach to multi-class HAR using GOTOV that balances performance with computational practicality.

3) EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

This subsection presents visualizations of representative samples from the dataset, showcasing the temporal patterns of sensor measurements collected from various body locations during different activities. Time-series visualizations provide valuable insight into the intrinsic characteristics of the signals, aiding the development of effective processing strategies. Fig. 6 presents a sample window from the *stacking shelves* activity, which exhibits a pattern that is difficult to distinguish. The sensor signals demonstrate comparable variances, with variations in elevation due to gravitational effects further obscuring activity-specific features.

4) DATA PREPROCESSING

In addition to the preprocessing strategies outlined in [41, p. 581], the following procedures are implemented to enhance the robustness and consistency of the dataset.

a: PARTICIPANT-LEVEL NORMALIZATION

Normalization is essential in Human Activity Recognition (HAR) to address inter-subject variability arising from sensor calibration discrepancies, anatomical differences, and

FIGURE 6. Sample window of sensor measurements for the stacking shelves activity.

environmental conditions. Robust scaling [48], based on the median and interquartile range (IQR), is employed to reduce the influence of outliers:

$$x' = \frac{x - \text{median}(x)}{\text{IQR}(x)} \quad (1)$$

b: DATA WINDOWING

Given the inherently temporal nature of human activities, raw time-series signals are segmented into fixed-length windows, either overlapping or non-overlapping. This segmentation process enables the preservation and extraction of temporal patterns essential for accurate activity classification [49]. The selection of window length and overlap ratio is driven by the temporal granularity necessary to capture discriminative characteristics across activity types.

c: NORMALIZATION TECHNIQUES

To standardize the input data and ensure suitability for downstream transformations, two normalization techniques are employed:

- **Local Normalization:** This approach is applied independently to each segmented window, scaling values within that window to the $[-1, 1]$ range. Local normalization is particularly advantageous for image-based transformations such as Gramian Angular Fields (GAF) [22], where individual window contrast is important. The transformation is defined as:

$$\text{Scaled Value} = \frac{(x - \text{Min}(x)) + (x - \text{Max}(x))}{\text{Max}(x) - \text{Min}(x)} \quad (2)$$

- **Global Normalization:** In contrast, global normalization preserves the relative magnitudes across all windows, which is important for maintaining inter-window consistency. It uses the global minimum and maximum values from the entire dataset [18]:

$$\text{Scaled Value} = \frac{(x - \text{MAX}) + (x - \text{MIN})}{\text{MAX} - \text{MIN}} \quad (3)$$

FIGURE 7. Comparison of local and global normalization strategies in both Cartesian and polar spaces.

FIGURE 8. Overview of the time-series imaging pipeline.

FIGURE 9. Sample imaging output for the *stacking shelves* activity.

Here, MAX and MIN denote the maximum and minimum values computed across the full dataset, respectively.

As the GAF technique involves transforming the time-series data from Cartesian to polar coordinates, we investigate the effects of local and global normalization in both Cartesian and polar domains. This comparison is visually illustrated in Fig. 7, highlighting the impact of each normalization strategy on the geometry of the signal.

d: TIME-SERIES IMAGING

Following normalization, each segmented time-series window is transformed into a two-dimensional image using time-series imaging techniques. Specifically, we evaluate three prominent methods: Gramian Angular Difference Field (GADF), Gramian Angular Summation Field (GASF), and Markov Transition Field (MTF). An overview of the imaging pipeline is provided in Fig. 8, while a representative image sample for the *stacking shelves* activity is shown in Fig. 9.

Among the evaluated methods, GADF consistently produces the most salient spatial-temporal representations. In contrast, MTF representations exhibit relatively lower informativeness, while GASF and Recurrence Plots (RP) offer moderate effectiveness. Based on these findings—and further supported by superior classification accuracy—GADF is selected as the primary imaging technique for this study.

e: LABEL ENCODING

Activity labels, initially represented as categorical strings, are converted into numerical format via integer encoding. As the

FIGURE 10. Overview of the proposed machine learning pipeline.

class labels are nominal rather than ordinal, this encoding scheme is both computationally efficient and compatible with most classification algorithms.

C. BUILDING AND TRAINING THE MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

Based on the architecture proposed in [18], an enhanced convolutional neural network (CNN) framework is developed, tailored specifically to the characteristics of the GOTOV dataset, which includes 16 distinct activity classes. An overview of the complete system architecture is presented in Fig. 10.

The proposed system comprises three independent CNN branches, each associated with one sensor location—ankle, wrist, or chest. These branches are designed to extract spatial-temporal features specific to each modality from the corresponding time-series imaging inputs. After training, the parameters of these branches are frozen to preserve learned representations during the subsequent fusion phase. The intermediate features are then concatenated and passed through a fusion module consisting of convolutional and fully connected layers. This hierarchical structure enables the integration of both local (sensor-specific) and global (cross-sensor) features, thereby improving multi-sensor activity recognition performance.

1) ARCHITECTURE OF THE INDEPENDENT CNN MODELS

The architecture of the independent CNN models is illustrated in Fig. 11. Each CNN branch is composed of three convolutional layers, each followed by a batch normalization layer to stabilize training and improve convergence. To enhance gradient flow and facilitate deeper feature learning, residual blocks are integrated within the architecture. The output of the final convolutional stage is passed through an adaptive average pooling layer, which ensures spatial dimensionality consistency. This is followed by a fully connected layer that produces a compact and discriminative feature representation suitable for subsequent classification.

2) ARCHITECTURE OF THE FUSION MODELS

Two fusion strategies are investigated to integrate the features extracted from the sensor-specific CNN branches.

FIGURE 11. Architecture of the proposed independent CNN models.

FIGURE 12. Architecture of the convolutional fusion model.

FIGURE 13. Architecture of the fully connected neural network fusion model.

The first, illustrated in Fig. 12, is a convolutional fusion architecture composed of two convolutional layers, each followed by batch normalization and residual connections. This configuration aids in maintaining spatial hierarchies and enhances deep feature learning. The second approach, shown in Fig. 13, is a fully connected neural network that employs a sequence of dense layers to implement a late fusion strategy. Both fusion architectures conclude with a softmax classifier, which estimates the probability distribution over the 16 predefined activity classes.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. DATASET PARTITIONING

Due to missing sensor readings in a substantial portion of the data, only participants with complete tri-axial accelerometer

measurements from the ankle, wrist, and chest were included. To ensure a balanced distribution across gender, age, height, weight, and body mass index (BMI), the dataset was further refined. The final subset comprises 20 participants, partitioned into training (12 participants), validation (4 participants), and testing (4 participants) sets. Participant exclusivity was maintained across these subsets to prevent information leakage, while efforts were made to preserve comparable demographic and physical characteristics distributions among them.

B. WINDOWING STRATEGY

Time-series data from each sensor location were segmented using a fixed-length, non-overlapping sliding window. To ensure that each segment corresponded to a single activity, windows that included label transitions were excluded. Notably, no overlap was applied even for consecutive samples with identical activity labels or from the same participant. This conservative approach ensures the integrity of each segment while simulating realistic deployment scenarios, where user data are typically processed in isolation.

C. TIME-SERIES TO IMAGE TRANSFORMATION

Each multivariate time-series window was transformed into an image using the Gramian Angular Difference Field (GADF). This method was selected after comparative evaluation against alternative imaging techniques, including the Gramian Angular Summation Field (GASF), Recurrence Plots, and Markov Transition Fields (MTF), with GADF demonstrating superior performance.

Each sensor modality generated four time-series signals: one magnitude and three normalized acceleration signals. Two normalization techniques—local and global normalization—were applied, producing eight distinct input channels per sensor. These channels were stacked into an RGB-like tensor serving as input to the CNN models.

D. MODELS ARCHITECTURE

Two model variants were implemented: (i) individual models per sensor location and (ii) fusion models aggregating features across all sensor locations.

1) SEPARATED MACHINE LEARNING MODELS: ARCHITECTURE DETAILS

The architectures of the individual models are illustrated in Fig. 11. Each model processes images from a specific body location (e.g., ankle, wrist, chest). The first convolutional layer receives 8 input channels and produces 16 output channels, using a 5×5 kernel, stride of 1×1 , and padding of 1×1 to preserve border information.

Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) functions are applied between layers, defined as:

$$f(x) = \max(0, x)$$

The second convolutional layer receives 16 channels and outputs 32 channels, with a kernel size of 3×3 , stride

2×2 , and padding 1×1 . The third convolutional layer outputs 64 channels with the same kernel size, stride, and padding as the second.

Each residual block consists of two convolutional layers with identical input/output dimensions, 3×3 kernels, stride 1×1 , and padding 1×1 . Each convolution is followed by batch normalization. A skip connection (identity shortcut) adds the input directly to the output of the block, enhancing gradient flow and enabling deeper feature learning.

The output tensor of 64 channels is reduced using an adaptive average pooling layer to a size of 1×1 per channel, yielding a 64×1 vector. This vector is passed to a fully connected layer with 16 neurons, each corresponding to one activity class, followed by a softmax activation:

$$\sigma(\mathbf{z})_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, K$$

2) FUSION MODEL ARCHITECTURE

The fusion model architecture is presented in Fig. 12. The output vectors (64×1) from the three individual models (ankle, wrist, chest), excluding their dense layers, are concatenated to form a single 192×1 vector.

This fused representation is passed to a convolutional layer that outputs 384 channels (i.e., 192×2). A subsequent convolutional layer increases this to 768 channels (192×4). Each convolutional layer is followed by batch normalization and a residual block identical in structure to those used in the independent models.

After the final residual block, adaptive average pooling reduces each of the 768 channels to size 1×1 , producing a 768×1 feature vector. This vector is passed to a fully connected layer with 16 output neurons and a softmax activation function.

E. MODELS TRAINING

Training was performed using the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer with a learning rate scheduler. The initial learning rate was set to 0.1 and was reduced by a factor of 10 if the validation loss plateaued over a specified number of iterations.

The loss function used was the multi-class cross-entropy with ℓ_2 regularization (penalty factor = 0.01):

$$\text{Multi-Class Cross-Entropy Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log(\hat{y}_{i,c}) \quad (4)$$

where C is the number of classes, $y_{i,c}$ is the ground truth indicator (0 or 1), and $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability.

To prevent gradient explosion, gradients were clipped to ensure their norm did not exceed 1. Each model was trained for 100 epochs. The fusion model was trained for 60 epochs due to its faster convergence, using the same training settings.

F. ADDRESSING DATASET IMBALANCE

To address class imbalance, a weighted loss function was employed during training.

1) CLASS WEIGHTING

Each class was assigned a weight inversely proportional to its frequency in the dataset. This ensures that minority classes exert greater influence on the loss, thereby enhancing their predictive performance.

The modified weighted cross-entropy loss is given by:

$$\text{Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^C w_j \cdot y_{ij} \cdot \log(p_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

where N is the total number of samples, C is the number of classes, w_j is the weight for class j , y_{ij} indicates if sample i belongs to class j , and p_{ij} is the predicted probability.

The class weight w_j was calculated using:

$$w_j = \frac{N}{C \cdot n_j} \quad (6)$$

where n_j is the number of samples in class j .

G. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE SETTINGS

The experiments were conducted on a Kaggle-hosted environment equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU @ 2.2 GHz, comprising 4 physical cores and supporting 2 threads per core (8 logical cores total). The system included 32 GB of RAM and an NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU with 16 GB of HBM2 memory, which was used for model training. All implementations were developed using the Python programming language.

1) SOFTWARE AND LIBRARIES

The implementation relied on several widely used Python libraries to facilitate data processing, visualization, and model development:

- `pyts` — for transforming time-series data into images using Gramian Angular Field (GAF) techniques.
- `NumPy` and `Pandas` — for numerical operations and structured data manipulation.
- `Matplotlib` and `Seaborn` — for visualization of raw signals, generated images, and performance metrics.
- `Scikit-learn` — for preprocessing tasks, including normalization and data partitioning.
- `PyTorch` — for constructing and training deep convolutional neural networks.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental results alongside a comprehensive analysis and discussion.

A. EVALUATION METRICS

Before reporting the results, the evaluation metrics employed to assess model performance are introduced. These metrics serve as quantitative criteria for model comparison and

FIGURE 14. Class distribution in the GOTOV training data.

evaluation. The following standard classification metrics were used:

- **Accuracy:** Accuracy represents the proportion of correctly predicted instances relative to the total number of predictions. Although widely used, its effectiveness is limited in imbalanced datasets. It is computed as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} \quad (7)$$

- **Precision:** Precision quantifies the proportion of true positive predictions among all predicted positives, reflecting the model’s ability to minimize false positives:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}} \quad (8)$$

- **Recall:** Also referred to as sensitivity, recall measures the model’s ability to identify all actual positives:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \quad (9)$$

- **F1 Score:** The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced metric that is particularly valuable in the context of class imbalance:

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (10)$$

- **Confusion Matrix:** A confusion matrix offers a comprehensive breakdown of prediction outcomes across all classes, including true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. It is instrumental in visualizing model performance and diagnosing class-specific misclassifications.

Given the high level of class imbalance in the dataset (illustrated in Figure 14), the F1 score was prioritized as the most informative evaluation metric.

B. SINGLE-MODAL MODEL RESULTS

Table 1 summarizes the performance of models trained on individual sensor modalities (e.g., Ankle, Wrist, and Chest), both with and without class balancing.

As shown in Table 1, the introduction of class balancing significantly improved performance across all metrics, particularly for underrepresented classes. Notably, the “walking stairs up” class—which was not detected by any unbalanced

TABLE 1. Performance metrics for different models. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Model	Accuracy	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
Ankle	77.04	65.23	67.79	65.55
Ankle-balanced	76.45	77.76	77.94	77.13
Wrist	72.26	65.54	63.85	62.99
Wrist-balanced	74.61	74.89	74.44	73.51
Chest	61.00	55.91	53.18	50.96
Chest-balanced	59.46	54.28	59.81	54.59

FIGURE 15. Confusion matrices for base models.

models—achieved full recall (100 %) in the Ankle and Chest balanced models, and 50 % in the Wrist balanced model.

Among the sensor modalities, the Ankle-based models achieved the highest overall performance, followed by Wrist, with Chest performing the worst. These results are consistent with the nature of human movement: ankle accelerations vary significantly across activities, while the chest remains relatively stationary, offering limited discriminative power. The confusion matrices in Figure 15 further validate these observations. For example, the Ankle-balanced model effectively distinguishes between dynamic activities like walking and cycling but struggles with static activities such as sitting on a chair versus a sofa. In contrast, the Wrist model provides better performance for hand-intensive activities like “Stacking Shelves” or “Dishwashing,” though it underperforms for lower-body-dominant activities. The Chest model, as anticipated, yields limited utility, contributing little to activity differentiation.

C. FUSION MODEL RESULTS

This section presents the results of multi-modal fusion models based on both CNN and fully connected neural network (NN) architectures. Table 2 summarizes the evaluation metrics for each fusion configuration, including different strategies for addressing class imbalance.

TABLE 2. Performance metrics for fusion models under different class balancing strategies. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Model	Accuracy	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
Fusion_CNN	78.07	75.33	71.51	70.72
Fusion_CNN_BA	78.29	73.35	71.28	70.21
Fusion_CNN_BB	78.07	77.96	75.53	74.84
Fusion_CNN_BBA	77.41	77.54	74.98	72.74
Fusion_NN	79.54	67.68	66.22	64.48
Fusion_NN_BA	81.68	77.82	79.12	76.66
Fusion_NN_BB	77.41	74.00	73.33	70.54
Fusion_NN_BBA	77.70	75.06	73.46	70.84

The reported fusion models are categorized based on how class imbalance was handled:

- No suffix (e.g., Fusion_CNN, Fusion_NN): Both the base models and the fusion model were trained using the standard (unweighted) loss function.
- BA (Balance After): Only the fusion model was trained with a class-weighted loss, while the base models used a standard loss function.
- BB (Balance Before): Base models were trained with class-weighted loss functions, whereas the fusion model used a standard loss function.
- BBA (Balance Before and After): Both the base models and the fusion model were trained with class-weighted loss functions.

Among the fusion models, the NN-based architecture with balanced training (Fusion-NN-BA) achieved the highest F1 score of 76.66%. Nevertheless, the Ankle-balanced single-modal model marginally outperformed this result with an F1 score of 77.13%, indicating that fusion does not always lead to improved performance. Moreover, less complex NN-based fusion models often outperformed deeper CNN-based architectures. This can be explained by the fact that the input features were already extracted by single-modality CNNs, making additional convolutional processing redundant. Furthermore, the larger parameter space in CNN-based fusion architectures increased optimization complexity and the risk of overfitting.

An analysis of class-wise performance revealed that individual models demonstrated varied strengths across different activity classes. Specifically, the ankle model exhibited superior accuracy for activities such as “Walking Stairs Up” and “Cycling,” the wrist model outperformed others in detecting the “Stacking Shelves” activity, and the chest model achieved the highest precision in the “Sync Jumping” activity. These findings motivated the design of a decision-level fusion strategy that leverages the class-wise precision of each model to guide the aggregation process.

1) PRECISION-WEIGHTED MODELS FUSION (PWMF)

The proposed PWMF architecture is illustrated in Figure 16, which depicts an example of a multi-class classification problem involving three models and four activity classes. Each model outputs a probability distribution over the classes. The fusion mechanism assigns a weight w_{ij} to the output

FIGURE 16. Overview of the proposed precision-weighted decision-level fusion architecture (PWMF).

of model i when predicting class j , where w_{ij} corresponds to the model’s precision for class j , calculated on the training or validation data. The final prediction is obtained by computing a weighted sum of model outputs and selecting the class with the highest aggregated score. The step-by-step implementation of the PWMF scheme is formalized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Precision-Weighted Model Fusion

Input:

- $mat1$: Precision matrix of shape ($number_models \times number_classes$)
- $mat2$: Prediction matrix of shape ($number_models \times number_classes$)

Output:

- $final_prediction$
- 1: Initialize $weighted_sum \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ (vector of length $number_classes$)
 - 2: **for each model do**
 - 3: $weighted_predictions \leftarrow mat1[model] \times mat2[model]$
 - 4: $weighted_sum \leftarrow weighted_sum + weighted_predictions$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: $final_prediction \leftarrow (weighted_sum)$
 - 7: **return** $final_prediction$
-

Precision was chosen as the weighting metric because it quantifies the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions for each class. This allows the fusion mechanism to prioritize models that are more reliable for specific classes. All precision scores were derived exclusively from training or validation data to prevent data leakage and preserve the integrity of the evaluation. Using test data for this purpose would compromise the objectivity and generalizability of the results.

D. PWMF FUSION ALGORITHM RESULTS

This subsection presents the performance of the Precision-Weighted Model Fusion (PWMF) algorithm on the GOTOV dataset. Class-wise precision values were computed using the

TABLE 3. Performance metrics for PWMF algorithm under different configurations. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Model	Accuracy	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWMF-all	87.05	87.44	83.79	83.39
PWMF-all-not-b	86.02	79.58	76.20	76.00
PWMF-all-b	86.39	87.52	83.52	82.38
PWMF-2a-2w	92.20	93.99	92.77	93.08

validation set and subsequently used to assign model weights for predicting the test set labels.

Four experimental configurations were designed to assess the effectiveness of PWMF under different base model conditions:

- 1) **PWMF-all**: Applied PWMF on six models (Ankle, Wrist, Chest, and their balanced counterparts).
- 2) **PWMF-all-not-b**: Applied PWMF on three unbalanced models (Ankle, Wrist, Chest).
- 3) **PWMF-all-b**: Applied PWMF on three balanced models (Ankle, Wrist, Chest).
- 4) **PWMF-2a-2w**: Applied PWMF on four models (Ankle and Wrist, both balanced and unbalanced), excluding the Chest modality.

The Chest modality consistently contributed minimal performance improvements. Therefore, in the PWMF-2a-2w configuration, it was intentionally excluded to evaluate whether performance could be enhanced using only ankle and wrist modalities.

Table 3 summarizes the performance metrics for all experimental scenarios.

From Table 3, it is evident that even the least effective PWMF configuration outperforms all previously tested CNN- and NN-based fusion models. Specifically, the lowest F1 score (76.00%) was obtained from the unbalanced model setup (PWMF-all-not-b), while the best configuration utilizing all six models (PWMF-all) achieved an F1 score of 83.39%. Notably, omitting the Chest modality (PWMF-2a-2w) led to a substantial performance gain, achieving an unprecedented F1 score of 93.08%.

Figure 17 presents the confusion matrices for the four PWMF configurations, providing a comparative overview of prediction performance across activity classes.

Given the superior performance of PWMF-2a-2w, we analyze its confusion matrix in further detail. As shown, the model demonstrates strong class discrimination capabilities, with the lowest true positive rate (81%) occurring only in a few challenging cases involving similar activities—such as “Dish Washing” vs. “Stacking Shelves”, “Sitting on Chair” vs. “Sitting on Sofa”, and “Walking Fast” vs. “Walking Normal”. Nevertheless, even in these cases, the model maintains a satisfactory level of accuracy.

Figure 18 depicts the per-class precision, recall, and F1 scores for the PWMF-2a-2w configuration. It can be observed that all activities exhibit F1 scores above 85%, with the exception of “SittingSofa”, which slightly falls below this threshold while still demonstrating robust performance.

FIGURE 17. Confusion matrices of the PWMF algorithm across four experimental configurations.

FIGURE 18. Per-class metrics (Precision, Recall, F1-score) for the PWMF-2a-2w configuration.

FIGURE 19. Comparative performance of all models across Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score.

1) COMPREHENSIVE COMPARISON ACROSS ALL EXPERIMENTS

To provide a holistic comparison of all implemented pipelines and experimental configurations, this paragraph summarizes their performance in terms of four standard metrics: Accuracy, Precision (macro-averaged), Recall (macro-averaged), and F1-score (macro-averaged). Figure 19 illustrates the relative performance of each approach, while Table 4 lists the corresponding numerical values.

As previously discussed, the balanced Ankle model and the NN-based fusion configurations show marked improvements

TABLE 4. Performance metrics of all developed pipelines and experiments. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Ankle	77.04	65.23	67.79	65.55
Ankle-Balanced	76.45	77.76	77.94	77.13
Wrist	72.26	65.54	63.85	62.99
Wrist-Balanced	74.61	74.89	74.44	73.51
Chest	61.00	55.91	53.18	50.96
Chest-Balanced	59.46	54.28	59.81	54.59
Fusion-CNN	78.07	75.33	71.51	70.72
Fusion-CNN-BA	78.29	73.35	71.28	70.21
Fusion-CNN-BB	78.07	77.96	75.53	74.84
Fusion-CNN-BBA	77.41	77.54	74.98	72.74
Fusion-NN	79.54	67.68	66.22	64.48
Fusion-NN-BA	81.68	77.82	79.12	76.66
Fusion-NN-BB	77.41	74.00	73.33	70.54
Fusion-NN-BBA	77.70	75.06	73.46	70.84
PWWF-all	87.05	87.44	83.79	83.39
PWWF-all-not-b	86.02	79.58	76.20	76.00
PWWF-all-b	86.39	87.52	83.52	82.38
PWWF-2a-2w	92.20	93.99	92.77	93.08

over their unbalanced counterparts. The proposed PWWF algorithm consistently outperforms all other models, with PWWF-2a-2w yielding the highest performance across all metrics. Specifically, PWWF-2a-2w achieved an F1-score of 93.08%, significantly surpassing other fusion and single-modality models. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of precision-weighted model fusion, particularly when excluding the Chest modality, which was found to contribute minimal discriminative value.

E. ABLATION STUDY FOR MODEL EFFICIENCY

Although our models demonstrated high performance, they contain an excessive number of deep layers. It remains uncertain whether all of these layers are truly essential, as this issue frequently arises in deep learning when numerous parameters contribute little to accuracy while substantially increasing computational cost. As stated in [50, p. 3], deep models can sometimes be oversized, which not only increases computational demands but also heightens the risk of overfitting.

To address this, we conducted an ablation study at the level of the residual blocks to evaluate their actual contribution. The main feature of a residual block is the skip connection, which facilitates deeper gradient flow [40]. However, our network already includes several convolutional layers that are sufficient for learning meaningful features from low-resolution, simple image-based time-series data. ResNet architectures were originally designed for high-resolution natural images rather than such simple inputs. Therefore, we removed the residual blocks entirely and replaced them with simplified skip connections incorporating projection layers to adapt the dimensional differences between consecutive convolutional layers.

The resulting lightweight architecture, termed **ResMinNet** (Residual Minimal Network), is illustrated in Fig. 20.

The projection layer aligns the two tensors to be added in both spatial and channel dimensions. Spatial alignment

FIGURE 20. Architecture of the proposed ResMinNet model per modality.**TABLE 5. Performance metrics for lightweight independent models compared with the baseline models (balanced versions only). Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric. The suffix “-b” denotes models trained with the balanced loss function.**

Model	F1-Macro	Parameters	FLOPs
Ankle-base-b	77.13	125,056	8.131M
Ankle-ResMiniNet-b	75.85	30,416	3.769M

is achieved through interpolation, while channel alignment is performed using a learnable 1×1 convolutional layer. Each projection layer may include an interpolation module, a 1×1 convolutional module, or both, depending on the dimensional differences between the skip connection and the main convolutional output.

In this study, the first convolutional layer employs a 5×5 kernel with a stride of 2 and padding of 2, resulting in downsampling from 64×64 to 32×32 . Consequently, a spatial projection using interpolation is required within the projection layer. The input has 8 channels, while the output of the first convolutional block contains 16 channels; therefore, a 1×1 convolutional layer with 16 filters follows the interpolation layer to match the channel dimensions.

The second and final convolutional layers both use 3×3 kernels with a stride and padding of 1, preserving the spatial resolution. However, their output channels increase from 32 to 64, respectively. Accordingly, the second and final projection layers each consist of a 1×1 convolutional layer with 32 and 64 filters, respectively.

The proposed model was evaluated on the GOTOV dataset using a balanced cost function to mitigate class imbalance. The results of the lightweight model are reported in Tables 5 and 6 and are compared with those of the corresponding baseline models trained under the balanced configuration. Models trained with unbalanced loss functions were excluded to minimize redundancy and computational cost.

Tables 5 and 6 present a comparison between the baseline Ankle-base-b and Wrist-base-b models and their lightweight counterparts, Ankle-ResMiniNet-b and Wrist-ResMiniNet-b, including the number of parameters and floating-point operations (FLOPs).¹

We observe that more than 75% of the trainable parameters were eliminated while maintaining a comparable level of accuracy with the lightweight model. This finding indicates that many parameters in the baseline models were redundant.

¹FLOPs refer to the number of *floating-point operations* required for a single forward pass, serving as a standard measure of computational complexity.

TABLE 6. Performance metrics for lightweight independent models compared with the baseline models (balanced versions only). Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric. The suffix “-b” denotes models trained with the balanced loss function.

Model	F1-Macro	Parameters	FLOPs
Wrist-base-b	73.51	125,056	8.131M
Wrist-ResMiniNet-b	71.28	30,416	3.769M

TABLE 7. Performance metrics of the PWMF algorithm applied to lightweight and baseline models. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Model	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWMF-2a-2w	93.99	92.77	93.08
PWMF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b	90.57	90.42	90.18

Moreover, the proposed design reduces the number of floating-point operations per forward pass by over 50%, resulting in significantly more efficient computation, particularly suitable for edge-device deployment.

We evaluated the PWMF algorithm on the lightweight models. In the previous PWMF experiment, we fused potentially redundant models, such as ankle and ankle-balanced with wrist and wrist-balanced. However, this duplication increased computational requirements while yielding only marginal accuracy gains. Since edge devices require models as lightweight as possible, we limited our experiments to the balanced versions only.

Table 7 presents the results of PWMF applied to the lightweight model, denoted as PWMF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b, compared with the PWMF-2a-2w configuration. We observe a marginal reduction in the F1 score, from approximately 93% to 90%. This decrease is negligible compared to the significant computational gain, corresponding to an approximate 88% reduction in the number of parameters, as PWMF-2a-2w uses four models.

We observe that PWMF improves the accuracy of individual models by approximately 15% to 20%. Therefore, it is essential to analyze this algorithm in depth and interpret the factors underlying its strong performance. In the following subsection, we present a mathematical analysis and interpretation of PWMF.

F. PWMF ALGORITHM ANALYSIS

1) PRINCIPLE AND MOTIVATION

Traditional model averaging methods, such as Bayesian Model Averaging (BMA) [51], assign a single, class-agnostic weight to each model. This approach assumes uniform reliability across all classes. In practice, however, models often perform better on certain classes than others. PWMF addresses this limitation by assigning class-specific weights to each model.

2) PWMF MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS

For each model M_i and class j , PWMF computes a reliability weight w_{ij} equal to the model’s precision for that class:

$$w_{ij} = \frac{TP_{ij}}{TP_{ij} + FP_{ij}}, \quad (11)$$

TABLE 8. Performance comparison of precision-, recall-, and F1-score-weighted model fusion for lightweight models. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Model	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWMF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b	90.57	90.42	90.18
RWMF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b	89.80	89.75	89.53
FWMF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b	89.79	89.70	89.46

where TP_{ij} and FP_{ij} denote the numbers of true positives and false positives, respectively, predicted by model M_i for class j .

Given an input sample x , each model M_i produces a probability vector $P(y = j | x, M_i)$. PWMF fuses these outputs using a reliability-weighted sum:

$$P(y = j | x, D) \approx \sum_{i=1}^M w_{ij} P(y = j | x, M_i), \quad (12)$$

where D denotes the validation dataset used for weight estimation. The final predicted label is:

$$\hat{y} = \arg \max_j P(y = j | x, D).$$

3) RELATION TO BAYESIAN MODEL AVERAGING (BMA)

PWMF can be viewed as a pragmatic approximation of BMA, which computes model weights as posterior probabilities:

$$P(M_i | D) \propto P(D | M_i)P(M_i),$$

where $P(D | M_i)$ is the model evidence and $P(M_i)$ is the prior belief about model M_i , usually assumed uniform. Computing $P(D | M_i)$ in deep learning models involves a complex integration over parameters, which is often intractable [52, p. 6].

PWMF replaces the posterior weight $P(M_i | D)$ with the empirical precision of each model on validation data:

$$w_{ij} \approx P(\text{model } M_i \text{ is correct} | \hat{y}_i = j),$$

which directly estimates the probability that the model’s prediction is correct for class j . Precision is preferred over recall or F1-score because recall measures coverage rather than correctness, and the F1-score combines precision and recall but does not directly represent the probability of a correct prediction. To validate this choice, we conducted experiments using recall- or F1-score-based weights instead of precision. The results are presented in Table 8. For convenience, we refer to the recall-weighted version as RWMF and the F1-weighted version as FWMF. The results demonstrate that PWMF consistently outperforms the alternatives, achieving the highest values across all evaluated metrics.

4) RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

The accuracy of the precision-based weight w_{ij} depends on the representativeness of the validation data. Hoeffding’s inequality [53] provides a probabilistic bound on the deviation between the empirical precision and the true reliability:

$$P(|w_{ij} - P(y = j | \hat{y}_i = j)| \geq \epsilon) \leq 2 \exp(-2n_{ij}\epsilon^2), \quad (13)$$

where w_{ij} denotes the empirical precision, $P(y = j | \hat{y}_i = j)$ represents the true reliability, $\epsilon > 0$ is the allowable deviation, and n_{ij} is the number of validation samples for class j . As n_{ij} increases, the probability of large deviations decreases, thereby enhancing the reliability of the estimated weights. Conversely, smaller n_{ij} values may lead to less accurate weight estimations.

5) COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS OF PWWF

The Precision-Weighted Model Fusion (PWWF) algorithm combines predictions from M models across C classes by performing element-wise multiplication of precision and prediction matrices followed by summation. This involves $O(M \times C)$ multiplications and additions, which is computationally negligible compared to CNN inference. PWWF introduces no additional trainable parameters and has zero extra inference time.

6) USE CASES, LIMITATIONS, AND POTENTIAL IMPROVEMENTS

PWWF is particularly effective when constituent models demonstrate heterogeneous performance across classes or modalities, allowing class-specific strengths to influence predictions. However, its benefits are limited when models exhibit similar performance uniformly across all classes. Additional limitations include reliance on static weights and sensitivity to the quality of validation data. Moreover, PWWF assumes complete and accurate inputs; missing or noisy data can degrade model reliability without proper detection. Potential improvements include implementing dynamic or online weight updating mechanisms based on new data or sensor feedback, as well as incorporating strategies to assess and adjust for input quality or sensor reliability.

G. INTERPRETABILITY OF PREDICTIONS

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) applications are critical in healthcare and elderly monitoring. Therefore, it is essential to understand how the convolutional neural network (CNN) models interpret image patterns to predict corresponding activities.

To this end, the well-known Grad-CAM method [54] was applied to the last convolutional layer of each individual ResMiniNet model (ankle and wrist). This technique generates gradient-based heatmaps that highlight the most salient regions contributing to the model's predictions. The heatmaps were subsequently upsampled to match the input dimensions, enabling visualization of the pixels in the images that most strongly influenced the prediction of specific activities. For this visualization, we specifically focused on channel 7, which corresponds to the amplitude of the global acceleration.

In this study, two representative activities are presented as examples: one straightforward activity, "Cycling" (Figure 21), and one challenging activity, "Dish Washing" (Figure 22).

FIGURE 21. Grad-CAM heatmap for sample 5 in channel 7 (amplitude of global acceleration). Pixels with higher intensity values (hotter colors) indicate regions more important for the model's prediction. The "ankle" and "wrist" labels correspond to the imaged windows from the respective sensor locations.

FIGURE 22. Grad-CAM heatmap for sample 2 in channel 7 (amplitude of global acceleration). Pixels with higher intensity values (hotter colors) indicate regions more influential in predicting the dishwashing activity. The "ankle" and "wrist" labels correspond to the imaged windows from the respective sensor locations.

The heatmap for "Cycling" reveals that the ankle model predominantly focuses on the periodic and regular motion patterns characteristic of this activity, particularly during the transition and cycling phases. Conversely, the wrist model exhibits a lower influence on the prediction of this activity, which aligns with the greater involvement of the ankle in cycling. In contrast, for the "Dish Washing" activity, the wrist model shows greater influence, reflecting the primary role of wrist movements in this task, while the ankle contributes less. Notably, the "Dish Washing" activity exhibits complex and subtle patterns that are difficult to discern by the human eye but are effectively captured by the machine learning model.

H. BENCHMARKING AGAINST LEADING METHODS ON THE GOTOV DATASET

To demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach, we compare our models with state-of-the-art human activity recognition (HAR) methods developed specifically for the GOTOV dataset. In particular, we benchmark against a prominent method proposed by Leiden University, the institution that originally released the GOTOV dataset.

Leiden University has published several studies utilizing this dataset. For instance, Paraschiakos et al. [41] grouped similar activities into broader categories to reduce the number of output classes and applied decision trees for classification. In a subsequent study, Okai et al. [45] employed

deep sequential models—specifically GRU and LSTM networks—to classify activities without class reduction, achieving a maximum average accuracy of approximately 85% using the full dataset with all three sensor modalities (Ankle, Chest, and Wrist).

In contrast, our study uses a subset of the GOTOV dataset, specifically data from participants without missing sensor measurements. Despite using fewer data samples, our models achieve competitive or superior performance, highlighting the efficiency of our approach.

To ensure a fair comparison, we re-implemented both the GRU and LSTM methods described in [45], using the same preprocessing steps except those intended to handle missing data (as our subset does not require such procedures). While the original study utilized the entire dataset from 35 participants, our implementation is based on data from only 20 participants with complete measurements.

The Chest modality consistently provided minimal benefit and, in some cases, even worsened fusion performance. Subsequent experiments excluding Chest data did not yield significant improvements and are therefore not discussed further.

1) BENCHMARK IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

In the original benchmark, the time-series data were used in their raw format, comprising concatenated readings from the three axes (x, y, z) of each sensor (Ankle, Chest, Wrist), resulting in 9-dimensional input per time step. Given that the Chest modality was excluded in our own approach due to its negative impact on classification accuracy, we also exclude it here to ensure consistency. Consequently, only the Ankle and Wrist modalities are used, each contributing three channels, resulting in a 6-dimensional input per time step. Each original window contained 500 time steps, yielding a total input size of $500 \times 6 = 3000$ data points per window.

To maintain consistency with our approach—where time-series images are resized from 500×500 to 64×64 (a downscaling ratio of approximately 1.64%)—we applied a similar adjustment to the raw time-series data. However, directly applying this scaling ratio would reduce each window to approximately nine time steps, leading to a significant loss in temporal resolution. To mitigate this, we adopted a less aggressive strategy by averaging every five consecutive time steps, thereby reducing each window to 100 time steps per channel. This results in a total of $100 \times 6 = 600$ data points per window, effectively balancing information preservation and computational efficiency.

The LSTM architecture used for benchmarking comprises an input layer with 6 neurons, followed by three hidden layers, each with 512 neurons, and a final output layer with 16 neurons corresponding to the number of activity classes. Although the original implementation employed a dropout rate of 50%, this was found to be overly aggressive for our comparatively smaller dataset. Through experimentation, we determined that a dropout rate of 20% between hidden layers yielded more stable and reliable performance.

FIGURE 23. Confusion matrices for LSTM and GRU under different configurations (with and without data undersampling).

The GRU-based model adopts the same architecture as the LSTM model, with the only modification being a reduced dropout rate of 10%, which improved performance in our empirical evaluations.

All remaining hyperparameters, training procedures, and optimization algorithms used in the benchmark implementation were kept consistent with those employed in our primary model to ensure a fair and uniform evaluation framework.

Due to class imbalance in our dataset subset, we conducted two versions of each benchmarking experiment: one using class balancing and the other without. For the balanced condition, we adopted the original study’s undersampling strategy to equalize class sizes. While the original benchmark’s smallest class contained 1286 samples, our dataset’s smallest class had only 23 samples. Accordingly, all classes were undersampled to 23 samples for fair comparison. To address limitations posed by such a small sample size, we also conducted two additional experiments using the full dataset without undersampling. In both the downsampled and full-data scenarios, batch-wise class balancing was applied, following the original study’s approach of randomly sampling batches to maintain approximately uniform class distribution during training.

2) BENCHMARKING RESULTS: PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the benchmarking results using the same evaluation metrics adopted for our proposed method. We begin with the confusion matrices, which provide a visual insight into model performance and serve as a precursor to interpreting the numerical evaluation metrics.

Figure 23 illustrates the confusion matrices for LSTM and GRU models under two configurations: with data undersampling (balanced dataset) and without data undersampling (imbalanced dataset).

As evident from the figure, the models performed poorly on the undersampled data. Consequently, those results are

TABLE 9. Performance metrics for LSTM, GRU, and our method (PWWF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b).

Model	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWWF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b	90.57	90.42	90.18
GRU-b	41.33	41.89	38.19
GRU-wb	50.37	46.89	42.79
LSTM-b	61.08	46.43	49.06
LSTM-wb	71.71	69.18	67.37

FIGURE 24. Per-class performance metrics for the LSTM model without data balancing (LSTM-wb).

excluded from the subsequent analysis. In contrast, the configurations without data balancing yielded relatively acceptable results. The diagonal dominance in the confusion matrices indicates logical and reasonable recognition performance, especially in the LSTM model.

Among the models, the GRU showed weaker performance overall, while the LSTM model demonstrated better results. For clearly distinguishable activities such as cycling and lying down (left or right), the LSTM achieved high classification accuracy. However, it struggled with similar activities that are difficult to differentiate—such as various forms of sitting (e.g., on a couch, chair, or sofa) or walking at different speeds (slow, normal, or fast). Additionally, it performed poorly on minority classes such as synchronized jumping, stepping, and walking upstairs, underscoring the limited effect of the class-balancing techniques applied.

Interestingly, the LSTM still achieved reasonable results on certain challenging activities, such as dishwashing, stacking shelves, and standing, likely due to these activities having relatively larger sample sizes. These observations suggest that the LSTM’s performance heavily depends on the quantity of available data and that the employed balancing method is suboptimal in addressing data imbalance. In contrast, our proposed method attained significantly better performance using less data, highlighting its robustness and efficiency.

Table 9 summarizes the performance metrics—Accuracy, Precision (Macro), Recall (Macro), and F1 Score (Macro)—for the four benchmarking experiments (LSTM and GRU with and without balancing), along with our lite best-performing model (PWWF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b).

Given that the LSTM-wb experiment yielded the best results among the benchmarking models, Figure 24 provides a detailed breakdown of its per-class metrics.

It can be observed that if similar activities—such as different types of walking or sitting—are merged, the LSTM

achieves an F1 score of at least 80%. However, its main limitation lies in its inability to discriminate between highly similar activity classes, a task challenging even for humans. This is precisely where our proposed approach demonstrates superior performance, excelling in fine-grained classification and maintaining high accuracy across both majority and minority classes.

I. COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION METHODS

Although our method was benchmarked against the best-performing model on the GOTOV dataset, which depends on long short-term memory (LSTM) networks, this model does not represent the state-of-the-art (SOTA) in human activity recognition (HAR) in general. To provide a more comprehensive evaluation, we compare our model with two leading HAR methods reported in the recent literature.

The first benchmark model, HARDenseRNN [55], achieved state-of-the-art performance on the WISDM 2019 dataset using a K-fold cross-validation protocol.² It combines multiple one-dimensional convolutional layers with various kernel sizes and residual connections, followed by a bidirectional gated recurrent unit (BiGRU) layer. The second benchmark, HART [56], is a lightweight transformer model designed for efficient HAR on mobile devices. HART processes accelerometer and gyroscope signals through sensor-wise convolutional layers and multi-head self-attention, followed by lightweight convolutional and feed-forward layers with global pooling. Despite its transformer-based architecture, which is typically computationally demanding, HART achieves an optimized balance between accuracy and efficiency for edge devices.

All methods were evaluated using identical data configurations, including user splits, sliding window parameters, and preprocessing steps, to ensure fair comparison. For both baseline methods, the raw sensor signals were used directly (without image transformation), and each window was downsampled from 500 to 100 samples. Two hyperparameter settings were tested: one aligned with our model configuration, and another replicating those reported in the original studies. The latter yielded better performance and was therefore adopted for the final comparison. Architectural details such as the number of layers, neurons, and activation functions were retained from the respective publications to ensure optimal performance.

Table 10 summarizes the training hyperparameters for all methods. For convenience, we refer to PWWF-ResMiniNet-a-w-b as PWWF-ResMiniNet in the subsequent comparisons.

Table 11 presents a comparison of classification performance metrics among different state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods and our approach (PWWF-ResMiniNet). We excluded

²K-fold cross-validation is a model evaluation strategy in which the dataset is divided into K subsets (folds). In each iteration, the model is trained on $K - 1$ folds and validated on the remaining one. This approach allows data from the same user to appear in both training and testing sets, meaning it does not enforce user independence.

TABLE 10. Training hyperparameters for our method and state-of-the-art baselines evaluated on the GOTOV dataset.

Method	Batch Size	Optimizer	Learning Rate	Weight Decay	Epochs
PWWF-ResMiniNet	512	SGD	adaptive	0.01	75
HARDenseRNN [55]	64	Adam	0.001	1×10^{-6}	75
HART [56]	128	Adam	0.0005	–	200

TABLE 11. Comparison of classification performance metrics (Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score) for SOTA methods and our proposed method (PWWF-ResMiniNet) on the GOTOV dataset. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Method	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWWF-ResMiniNet	90.57	90.42	90.18
HARDenseRNN [55]	85.70	80.34	80.28
HART [56]	84.52	86.22	83.73

TABLE 12. Computational complexity comparison of state-of-the-art methods and our proposed method (PWWF-ResMiniNet), including trainable parameters and floating-point operations (FLOPs) required for a single forward pass. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Method	Trainable Parameters	FLOPs
PWWF-ResMiniNet	$2 \times 30,416 = 60,832$	3.769M
HARDenseRNN [55]	357,884	22.057M
HART [56]	1,461,606	57.85M

LSTM and GRU models from this comparison as they were discussed previously and are not considered SOTA methods. Table 12 shows the computational performance of these methods in terms of trainable parameters and floating-point operations (FLOPs).

Our method demonstrates a superior F1-score compared to existing approaches, despite HARDenseRNN achieving higher accuracy. Since accuracy is not a reliable metric for this unbalanced dataset, F1-score serves as a more appropriate performance measure. As shown in Table 12, our model has only about 17% of the parameters and requires just 17.1% of the FLOPs compared to HARDenseRNN. Compared to HART, our model uses roughly 4.2% of the parameters and 6.5% of the FLOPs. This substantial reduction in computational complexity is crucial for efficient inference on wearable edge devices used in human activity recognition, where resource constraints demand high performance without compromising accuracy. These results highlight the exceptional suitability of our method for deployment in such environments.

J. GENERALIZATION TO OTHER DATASETS

To evaluate the generalizability of our method to other human activity recognition (HAR) datasets, we conducted experiments on two challenging benchmarks: PAMAP2 [43] and WISDM 2019 [44].

1) EXPERIMENTS ON THE PAMAP2 DATASET

The PAMAP2 dataset contains sensor data recorded from nine participants performing twelve essential activities (e.g., standing, walking, ironing) and six optional activities (e.g., watching TV, driving). Due to the rarity of some optional

TABLE 13. Classification performance metrics of state-of-the-art methods and our method (PWWF-ResMiniNet) on the PAMAP2 dataset. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Method	Precision (Macro)	Recall (Macro)	F1-score (Macro)
PWWF-ResMiniNet	89.34	86.23	87.36
HARDenseRNN [55]	76.11	75.28	74.48
HART [56]	86.47	85.48	84.68

activities—several performed by only one participant—we focus solely on the twelve essential activities. This dataset is particularly challenging because of the limited number of participants.

Participants wore three inertial measurement units (IMUs) on the ankle, chest, and wrist, each recording accelerometer and gyroscope signals. Consistent with our approach on the GOTOV dataset, we exclude the chest sensor. We use only acceleration data along the three axes (x, y, z) plus the magnitude, resulting in eight channels after local and global normalization.

Data are segmented into non-overlapping windows of 520 samples. Given the IMU sampling frequency of 100 Hz, each window corresponds to 5.2 seconds of data. These windows are then transformed into images with dimensions $8 \times 520 \times 520$, which are subsequently resized to $8 \times 100 \times 100$ pixels due to memory constraints. For each modality (ankle and wrist), a separate ResMiniNet model is trained (see Figure 20), and predictions are fused using PWWF.

For the competing methods HARDenseCNN and HART, we use the same windowing scheme but operate on raw data rather than images. Specifically, we apply global normalization and downsample each 520-sample window to 104 samples by averaging every five consecutive samples to ensure a fair comparison with our image-based approach. Additionally, these methods use a single model trained on concatenated ankle and wrist data, resulting in eight-channel input windows.

Hyperparameters are consistent across methods and follow those in Table 10, except that the batch size for HART is reduced to 32 to improve performance. We split the dataset by participant, ensuring no participant's data appears in more than one subset. The training set comprises subjects 102, 103, 104, 106, 107, 108, and 109; the validation set contains only participant 101; and the test set includes participant 105.

Table 13 summarizes the classification performance of our method compared to the baselines on the PAMAP2 dataset. Here, the two ResMiniNet models corresponding to the ankle and wrist sensors fused using PWWF are collectively referred to as PWWF-ResMiniNet.

We observe that our method outperforms all other approaches across all evaluated metrics. Although HART achieves results close to ours, its significantly higher computational requirements are not justified given the marginal difference in performance. It is important to emphasize the effectiveness of PWWF in handling high-variance modalities such as ankle and wrist data. For instance, the independent ankle model achieved an F1-score of only 65.84% on the

test set, and the wrist model achieved 70.44%. In contrast, the PWWF algorithm improved the F1-score to 87.36%, representing an improvement of over 15%. This performance gain demonstrates the advantage of PWWF in leveraging the complementary information from diverse modalities, as previously discussed.

2) EXPERIMENTS ON THE WISDM 2019 DATASET

The WISDM 2019 dataset contains acceleration and gyroscope measurements collected from smartwatches and smartphones worn by 51 participants performing 18 different activities, such as walking, eating pasta, and eating sandwiches, among other challenging tasks. Our study focuses exclusively on data from wearable sensors; therefore, we use only the smartwatch data and exclude smartphone data.

A key contribution of our work is the fusion algorithm, PWWF, which we apply to combine acceleration and gyroscope data from the smartwatch. Although these sensors are co-located, they represent distinct modalities. However, the variance between acceleration and gyroscope signals from the same sensor is lower than that between completely different sensors. As discussed in the PWWF algorithm section, PWWF excels in fusing highly variant modalities; thus, we anticipate smaller improvements here. Nonetheless, PWWF still enhances performance due to the existing differences between modalities.

The smartwatch samples data at 20 Hz. We segment the time series into non-overlapping windows of 256 samples, corresponding to approximately 12.8 seconds. Each window undergoes local and global normalization, then is processed through an imaging pipeline to produce 256×256 pixel images with eight channels per modality (acceleration and gyroscope). These channels represent the x, y, and z axes readings and their magnitudes under both normalization schemes. Due to computational constraints, the images are resized to 128×128 pixels. Due to computational constraints, we limited our study to data from 20 subjects. While this subset is smaller than the full dataset, it is sufficiently representative for the purposes of our experiments.

The dataset is split strictly by participant to prevent data leakage: 12 subjects (IDs 1600–1611) for training, 4 (1612–1615) for validation, and 4 (1616–1619) for testing. We train separate models for acceleration and gyroscope data, then fuse their predictions using PWWF. All methods use the same data segmentation for fair comparison.

In contrast, HARDenseCNN and HART utilize raw time-series data. For HARDenseCNN, windows are downsampled from 256 to 128 samples via average pooling of every two consecutive samples to align with our image resizing. HART uses the full 256-sample windows, as downsampling degraded its performance. Both methods concatenate acceleration and gyroscope data, resulting in eight-channel input windows. Normalization differs: only one normalization type is applied.

Hyperparameters for all methods are consistent with those listed in Table 10, except for HART's number of epochs,

TABLE 14. Performance metrics for SOTA methods and our method (PWWF-ResMiniNet) on the WISDM 2019 dataset. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Method	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWWF-ResMiniNet	78.07	77.05	76.09
HARDenseRNN [55]	76.15	74.31	73.45
HART [56]	66.21	64.02	63.40

which was set to 100 due to early convergence. The batch size for our method was set to 64, as this configuration yielded higher accuracy on the current dataset, while the number of training epochs was reduced to 40. Table 14 presents a comparison of accuracy metrics between our method, HARDenseCNN, and HART. Here, the ResMiniNet models corresponding to the accelerometer and gyroscope sensors fused using PWWF are collectively referred to as PWWF-ResMiniNet.

Our method consistently demonstrates superior performance compared to the state of the art while maintaining impressive computational efficiency. Under the current dataset splitting and experimental configuration, our method outperforms competing approaches. Although HARDenseCNN achieves similar performance, it incurs significantly higher computational overhead compared to our method.

It is worth revisiting the efficiency of the PWWF fusion algorithm. The single acceleration model achieves an F1 score of approximately 70%, while the gyroscope model achieves around 66%. Fusion of these modalities improves the F1 score to approximately 76%, representing an improvement of about 6 percentage points over the acceleration model alone. Since both modalities originate from a single body location (the wrist) and represent different sensors (gyroscope and accelerometer), the variation in per-class performance is limited. Consequently, the improvement from PWWF fusion is smaller than that observed when fusing more diverse data sources. For example, in the PAMAP2 and GOTOV datasets, PWWF achieves improvements of at least 15 percentage points in F1 score. Nevertheless, the 6% improvement observed here remains meaningful despite the relatively small difference between accelerometer and gyroscope data from the same device.

An inconsistency was observed between the HARDenseRNN results reported on the WISDM 2019 dataset in the original paper [55] and those obtained in our experiments. This discrepancy arises from differing evaluation protocols. The original study employed a k-fold cross-validation approach that did not exclude participants from the training set, allowing data from all users to be present in both training and testing folds. This practice leads to data leakage, rendering the evaluation unreliable for assessing generalizability to unseen users.

To replicate the original results, the same evaluation protocol and data configuration were adopted, using overlapping windows of length 256 samples and a stride of 32, and training for 120 epochs as specified. This yielded results

TABLE 15. Performance metrics for SOTA methods and our method (PWF-ResMiniNet) using a single-fold cross-validation protocol on WISDM 2019. Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Method	Precision-Macro	Recall-Macro	F1-Macro
PWF-ResMiniNet	96.19	96.19	96.18
HARDenseRNN [55]	98.31	98.29	98.29
HART [56]	81.23	81.18	81.05

comparable to those reported. The protocol was then applied to our method by merging windows from all subjects, shuffling, and splitting them into training, validation, and testing sets. Data were segmented into windows of 256 samples with a stride of 32 and without downsampling to ensure comparability. The data were then transformed into images resized to 32×32 pixels due to memory constraints. Despite this aggressive resizing and the lighter architecture, our method achieved results comparable to HARDenseCNN under this protocol (see Table 15). The experiments were also executed using the HART method and results are reported in Table 15. Due to computational limitations, only a single-fold cross-validation was conducted, involving one round of training and testing. Under this protocol, HARDenseCNN marginally outperformed our method. However, this evaluation setup is not practical as it does not simulate the scenario of unseen end-users during training and suffers from data leakage. HART showed worse performance than both our method and HARDenseRNN. This can be explained by the fact that the transformer is not suitable for small data [57], and in our experiments, the data is small.

Moreover, HARDenseRNN, HART, and the single ResMiniNet models exhibited near-perfect training accuracy on the WISDM 2019 datasets when participants were strictly separated across sets, as shown in Figures 25 and 26, which present confusion matrices for training and testing data across the three methods. This indicates that the models primarily learn personalized patterns of complex tasks (e.g., eating various foods) rather than generalizable activity patterns. In contrast, the k-fold cross-validation protocol allows the models to observe all pattern variations, leading to higher reported accuracy but limited generalizability.

Our method demonstrates reduced overfitting due to the ensemble effect of combining two models, which decreases variance. Nevertheless, an important challenge remains: generalization to certain activities remains particularly difficult. For example, activities such as eating chips or eating a sandwich exhibit high variability between individuals, and the subtle differences in movement patterns when performing these tasks make it challenging for the models to generalize well to unseen users. Although the method is strong at discriminating the overall activity category (e.g., eating), it struggles to differentiate between types of eating (e.g., chips, sandwich). Therefore, limitations persist in generalizing these subtle and challenging tasks. This issue warrants further research and opens avenues for future research.

Overall, our method consistently demonstrates superior performance compared to state-of-the-art approaches across

FIGURE 25. Confusion matrices for HARDenseRNN and HART on WISDM 2019 training and testing sets.

FIGURE 26. Confusion matrices for the single ResMiniNet models based on accelerometer and gyroscope data on the training and testing sets of the WISDM 2019 dataset, as well as for the PWF-fused predictions on the testing set.

all datasets while maintaining impressive computational efficiency. This positions our developed CNN architecture, ResMiniNet, combined with the PWF fusion algorithm, as one of the most effective methods for human activity recognition pipelines applicable to various HAR tasks.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research makes a significant contribution to the field of human activity recognition (HAR) using wearable sensors through the development of the novel *PWF-ResMiniNet* framework. Inspired by methods proposed in the literature

that transform time-series signals into images for convolutional neural network (CNN) analysis, we focused on the underexplored GOTOV dataset and established a new benchmark performance. To our knowledge, this is the first study in the literature to achieve an F1-score exceeding 90% on the GOTOV dataset.

The *PWWF-ResMiniNet* approach converts time-series data into Gramian Angular Field (GAF) images and employs a CNN architecture inspired by ResNet. Separate models were trained for sensors placed on the ankle, wrist, and chest. Empirical analysis revealed that the chest sensor contributed minimally to activity discrimination, and thus it was excluded. To address class imbalance, we applied a weighted loss function during training.

Several fusion strategies were examined, including CNN-based and neural network-based approaches. However, these methods provided no accuracy improvement and increased computational cost. Consequently, we developed a simple yet effective decision-level fusion algorithm, termed *Precision-Weighted Model Fusion* (PWWF). This novel method eliminates the need for heavy fusion architectures, operates with negligible inference time, and improved individual model performance by 15–20%. Subsequent ablation experiments on CNN structures led to the design of a compact architecture, *ResMiniNet*, which reduces approximately 75% of trainable parameters with only marginal accuracy loss, largely compensated by PWWF. Our lightweight *PWWF-ResMiniNet* framework outperformed benchmark LSTM and GRU models on the GOTOV dataset, as well as advanced approaches such as HARDenseRNN and HART, achieving superior accuracy with substantially lower computational complexity.

To validate generalizability, we further evaluated *PWWF-ResMiniNet* on two additional benchmark datasets, PAMAP2 and WISDM 2019, where it consistently outperformed state-of-the-art methods in both accuracy and efficiency.

Despite its strengths, the *PWWF-ResMiniNet* framework has limitations. The conversion of time-series windows into GAF images remains computationally demanding and increases preprocessing time. Future work should aim to optimize this step and explore unified normalization schemes to reduce memory consumption. Further studies are also needed to evaluate the potential benefits of incorporating signal amplitude information and refining the transformation of precision values within PWWF. Computational constraints prevented the use of complete datasets for GOTOV and WISDM 2019, suggesting that extended experiments are warranted.

Additionally, improving model interpretability and developing explainable mechanisms for recognizing complex activity patterns represent valuable future directions. Generalization across users and fine-grained activities remains a challenging open problem. Although using multiple sensors (ankle and wrist) enhances performance, this configuration may be impractical for everyday use. Designing approaches that achieve comparable accuracy with a single

wearable device would increase usability. Moreover, *PWWF-ResMiniNet* cannot yet recognize unseen activities, highlighting the importance of zero-shot HAR as a promising research avenue. Finally, robustness against sensor noise or failure must be addressed to ensure real-world applicability.

In summary, this work demonstrates that the *PWWF-ResMiniNet* framework offers a systematic, interpretable, and computationally efficient multimodal sensor fusion approach that achieves state-of-the-art performance without relying on excessively complex deep learning architectures.

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MOHAMMAD SAKKA received the B.Eng. degree in computer and automation engineering from Damascus University, Syria, in 2019, and the M.Sc. degree in data analysis and artificial intelligence from Innopolis University, in 2024, on a fully funded scholarship, where he is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the Department of Computer Science and Engineering. From 2020 to 2022, he was a Teaching Assistant with the Faculty of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering, Damascus University, and concurrently worked as a Research and Development Algorithm Engineer. In 2024, he was awarded a fully funded scholarship to pursue his Ph.D. He has authored two peer-reviewed publications (one journal article and one conference paper) and one preprint. He currently serves as a founding AI engineer at a major technology startup. His research interests include computational intelligence, signal and image processing, machine learning, knowledge inference, healthcare applications, and sensor fusion. He received the Award for Academic Excellence from Damascus University and was recognized among the top students of his cohort.

OSAMA ORABI is currently pursuing the bachelor's degree with Innopolis University, Russia. He is a Researcher with Innopolis University. He is affiliated with the Quantum Computing Laboratory, Innopolis University, where his research applies artificial intelligence methods—particularly deep learning—to quantum computing and related domains. His current work focuses on developing intelligent systems based on modern neural network architectures and their integration with quantum computing techniques. He has been recognized for his outstanding academic and research achievements, receiving the Student of the Year Award at Innopolis University for two consecutive years. He also won three hackathons in Russia centered on solving complex problems using artificial intelligence, including a nationally significant event that received a certificate of recognition from the Prime Minister of Tatarstan.

YAZAN ALNAKRI is currently pursuing the Bachelor of Science degree in computer science, with a specialization in data science. He is a middle-level Machine Learning Engineer and a Researcher with Innopolis University, Russia. He is a Main Machine Learning Developer with an AI Solutions startup. His professional experience includes developing and deploying artificial intelligence solutions in both academic and industrial settings, with a focus on computer vision, natural language processing, and retrieval-augmented generation systems. He has participated in numerous AI projects and competitions, earning recognition in national and regional hackathons. His research interests include multimodal learning, large language models, graph neural networks, and the integration of AI techniques for real-world applications.

MOHAMMAD REZA BAHRAMI received the Ph.D. degree in mechanical engineering from Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, St. Petersburg, Russia, in 2016. He was an Assistant Professor with Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, from 2016 to 2018, and with Innopolis University, from 2018 to 2022. In May 2022, he became an Associate Professor. From January 2023 to November 2025, he was appointed as the Head of the Cyber-Physical Systems Laboratory. In September 2023, he also served as the Head of Laboratories Center, Samarkand International University of Technology (SIUT). Since September 2025, he has been the Dean of the School of Engineering, he has led major curriculum reforms, launched new degree programs, developed transition plans for existing curricula, and coordinated faculty efforts to ensure accreditation compliance and alignment with industry needs. Throughout his academic career, he has supervised more than 50 graduate and undergraduate theses in mechanical engineering and computer science. In addition, he has over ten years of industry experience. He is proficient with digital learning platforms, including Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Moodle, Notion, and GitHub. His publication record includes four books, 18 book chapters (Springer), 25 journal, and procedia papers, and 35 full conference papers (including venues such as IFToMM). His scholarly contributions led to his recognition as a 2024 Top Scholar by ScholarGPS, placing him among the Top 0.5% of Researchers worldwide in research impact and publication quality. He has received over 4 870 000 rubles (approximately 100 000 USD) in awards, prizes, and research funding. He has extensive teaching experience in offline, online, and hybrid formats, and has taught large cohorts of up to 350 students.

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